

Title: Towards inclusive urban transitions: An intersectional analysis of reuse and repair grassroots initiatives in Barcelona

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Ethics Declarations

This study was approved by the Autonomous University Ethics Committee (approval no. CEEAH 6915) and informed consent has been obtained by all participants of the study.

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Abstract

This article examines how grassroots repair/reuse initiatives in Barcelona both contest and reproduce social hierarchies. Using an intersectional framework, we analyse how systems that reproduce dynamics related to gender, age, racialisation, class, as well as local political-economic contexts interact to shape participation, visibility, and authority in two initiatives: Restart Parties (community electronics repair events) and Libraries of Things (tool/object lending). The study draws on participant observation at Restart Parties and Libraries of Things, four focus groups and 33 semi-structured interviews with organizers, repairers, users, and institutional actors. We identify recurring mechanisms of exclusion, including adultism and housing-linked youth marginalization; linguistic dominance and racialized belonging that narrow migrant participation; gendered divisions of labour and “mansplaining” that confine women to organizing or “user” roles; knowledge/authority asymmetries and efficiency-oriented practices that privilege fixing over pedagogy; temporal dispossession linked to neoliberal work/care regimes; and cultural/economic dynamics (gentrification, social status, fees) that filter access. At the same time, we document counter-tendencies such as school-based mini-libraries, women/non-binary mechanics trainings, flexible fee practices, and “explain-while-doing” approaches that open pathways to technical agency and community empowerment. We contribute to intersectional environmental justice and circularity debates by specifying how multiple axes of domination at both micro and macro levels intersect in situated grassroots circular settings, and we discuss strategies to make repair/reuse culture more inclusive and accessible.

Keywords: repair/reuse grassroots, circularity, intersectionality, inclusivity, exclusion

1. Introduction

Repair/reuse initiatives have gained visibility in sustainability and circularity scholarship (e.g., Purvis et al., 2025; Gobert et al., 2021; Hernandez et al., 2020). Beyond extending the lifespan of objects, they create spaces for knowledge-sharing (Houston, 2019), community engagement (Callen & Duque, 2023; Pansera et al., 2024), solidarity, and alternative consumption practices (Rogers et al., 2021). Yet these initiatives are not immune to reproducing social hierarchies and exclusions (Barca, 2023). How these dynamics influence repair/reuse initiatives remains an underexplored question, particularly from a perspective attentive to broader power relations and inequality as well as micro-gestures. Understanding these dynamics is essential if repair and reuse aim to contribute meaningfully to more just and inclusive socio-ecological transformations.

This article addresses this gap by adopting an intersectional framework (McCall, 2005) to analyse how multiple hierarchical systems interact in shaping exclusion/inclusion dynamics of repair/reuse practices. Intersectionality allows us to move beyond additive models of disadvantage and instead interrogate how systems that produce categories such as

gender, age, class, and migration background intersect to shape participation, visibility, and agency. Empirically, we examine Restarters BCN and Libraries of Things/Tools (LoTs), two community-based initiatives in Barcelona. These cases illuminate how grassroots circular practices are shaped by, and respond to, intersecting inequalities. We ask: How do repair/reuse initiatives respond to dynamics of exclusion and inclusion? To what extent do they reproduce or contest broader social hierarchies?

2. Intersectional approach of repair and reuse: inclusions and exclusions in grassroots initiatives

Intersectionality is a critical framework for examining the interconnectedness of social categories and systems of power. These categories are socially constructed, historically contingent, and politically instrumentalized. Originating in Black feminist scholarship (Crenshaw, 1989), the lens now encompasses marginalizations tied to migration, colonialism, disability, transgender identity, and homelessness (Acheson et al., 2024). Racism, patriarchy, economic disadvantage, and related power regimes produce interconnected inequalities that shape specifically group positions. Accordingly, intersectionality calls for multilevel cross analysis linking lived experience to social institutions and power structures such as law, policy and culture (Atewologun, 2018). While intersectionality has expanded beyond its original focus on the interlocking effects of race, gender, and class (Crenshaw, 1989), this expansion has not been without contestation. Scholars have cautioned that unbounded or universal applications risk diluting intersectionality's roots in Black feminist thought and re-marginalising Black women (Chantler & Thiara, 2017). In this study, though, we approach intersectionality as non-essentialistic; not as an additive framework of disadvantage (Howard & Renfrow, 2014), but as a context-sensitive analytic lens attentive to how historically specific constellations of different kinds of power take shape in particular socio-spatial settings. In this sense, identities appear as non-static, fluid, and contextually embedded (Cho et al., 2013). Crucially, this approach rejects single-axis explanations (e.g., class over gender or race), since “oppression is produced through the interaction of multiple, decentred, and co-constitutive axes” (Carastathis, 2014: 308). Accordingly, our analysis focuses on structural power and inequalities as shaped in particular contexts approaching identities as effects of these oppressions (Goikoetxea et al., 2019). In the case of grassroots repair and reuse initiatives in Barcelona, this entails examining how different systems of oppression intersect in practice, remaining attentive to their unequal structural weight and historical grounding. Our use of intersectionality is thus empirically anchored and politically situated.

Building on intersectionality's expansion beyond gender and race, environmental justice scholarship and activism increasingly use it to show that climate and ecological crises are inseparable from racism, colonialism, patriarchy, ableism, and classism. While environmental justice has long examined how environmental harms reflect oppressive social relations, intersectionality adds crucial contextual and critical depth to these analyses (Di Chiro, 2021). Rather than treating ecological injustices as isolated incidents, it situates them within long-standing historical, institutional, and multi-scalar structures of domination (Malin & Ryder, 2018). Accordingly, justice demands more than technical fixes; it requires acknowledging how racialized, gendered, colonial, and class-based oppressions are mutually reinforcing and structurally embedded. At the same time, an intersectional lens foregrounds

agency: experiences of oppression can be leveraged as knowledge and political strength, enabling grassroots strategies that reimagine socio-ecological relations from below (see Amorim-Maia et al., 2022).

This orientation appears in research on environmental justice struggles around waste. Studies of grassroots mobilisation against toxic dumping, for instance, show how intersectional politics shape both diagnostic framings and repertoires of action, especially among communities marginalised by race, class, and indigeneity (Pellow, 2016). Climate justice and intersectionality share radical-theory roots, foregrounding power relations and challenging dominant epistemologies about nature and human-nature relations (Mikulewicz et al., 2023). Yet intersectionality remains under-integrated in sustainability transitions and waste studies, limiting attention to power, inequality and political subjectivity (Acheson et al., 2024). Earlier work mainly nuanced vulnerability analyses (e.g., Indigenous women's exclusion from climate policymaking), whereas current scholarship explicitly links intersectionality to a transformative climate-justice agenda, shifting from documenting harm to dismantling individual and structural architectures of marginalization and envisioning equitable, sustainable responses (Mikulewicz et al., 2023; Amorim-Maia et al., 2022). Agency is central as communities at multiple axes of oppression convert marginalization into collective power for bottom-up strategies.

Within repair and reuse scholarship, mounting evidence shows how repair intersects with hierarchical relations of class, race, gender, and expertise, shaping access and benefit from knowledge exchange. Feminist work highlights the persistent undervaluation of reproductive labour, including maintenance and care, even within alternative cultures (Pansera et al., 2024), and grassroots initiatives often reflect male-dominated structures in technical roles, thereby perpetuating gender divides rather than challenging them (Rosner, 2014). In this sense, women are frequently relegated to care-coded tasks such as garment mending, while men dominate technical/mechanical repairs (Rogers et al., 2021; van der Velden, 2021; Schäggen et al., 2022). Hence, these patterns shape not only volunteers but also visitors, whose expectations and contributions are filtered through prevailing norms (Young & Rosner, 2019).

At the same time, other studies point to how community repair can unsettle gendered divisions and positively influence participation in technical work (van der Velden, 2021). In this way, analyses illustrate both the persistence of traditional roles and possibilities for their reconfiguration, including women-focused workshops for power tools and home repairs (Young & Rosner, 2019), such as women-only "Rosie the Restarter" sessions (van der Velden, 2021; Graziano & Trogal, 2017), and women-only Repair Cafés or bike repair spaces for refugees (Schäggen et al., 2022). These have broadened technical participation without the pressure of traditional gender expectations and successfully included lower income, including refugees as technical volunteers and paid staff.

Intersectional analyses also foreground macro-level constraints. Repair/reuse efforts operate within social, institutional, and technical lock-ins: negative public perceptions, limited institutional support and market designs that privilege low-cost, irreparable goods (Gobert et al., 2021). Explaining the long-run decline of repair, Cooper and Salvia (2018) identify economic, psychological, sociocultural, and political forces that drive replacement sales in mass consumerism. Across studies, six recurring barriers appear: (1) limited

knowledge of how products work and missing whole-life-cost information; (2) lack of spare parts, technical information, and restrictive contracts; (3) damage beyond repair; (4) weak economic incentives to repair; (5) limited engagement or affective attachment to products; and (6) design/manufacturing that inhibits repairability (Lechner et al., 2021; Hernandez et al., 2020). In response, coalitions across communities and causes can widen participation (Azmitia et al., 2023). What remains underexplored in such accounts is how these constraints intersect with social hierarchies to shape participation, recognition, and exclusion within repair spaces and how macro-level mechanisms translate into micro-level dynamics and effects.

Intersectional perspectives on repair, reuse, and waste must further interrogate how inequalities shape participation in circularity and what forms of exclusion emerge. For this reason, this article adopts intersectionality as an analytic framework to examine the power dynamics that enable or constrain inclusivity in grassroots repair/reuse initiatives, and to clarify how such dynamics may reproduce exclusions even within practices aimed at just sustainability and social change.

3. The case of Libraries of Things/Tools and Restarters in Barcelona

Barcelona hosts a growing number of grassroots repair and reuse initiatives that seek to extend objects' lifespans, circulate goods through shared use, and cultivate practical knowledge and mutual support around everyday consumption. Restarters initiative and LoTs function as a coupled community infrastructure for circularity: Restarters mobilizes repair know-how and socio-technical learning, while the LoTs provide tools' lending services, and a steady flow of everyday objects and users. In the districts of Sant Marti and Ciutat Vella, these two initiatives co-habit in the same space and work as mutually reinforcing projects (e.g., repair volunteers diagnose and fix items from the Libraries' inventories, while Libraries channel users, tools, and objects into repair events (and vice versa)).

Restarters BCN Initiative

Barcelona's Restarters collective, set up in 2015, draws on the London-based "The Restart Project". Its core aim, according to participants, is to counter premature obsolescence by giving support to the creation of local repair communities and hosting public "Restart Parties", free public events where volunteers with technical skills help participants repair their own electrical and electronic devices in a relaxed and community-based environment. But its objectives go further: "the Restart Project's aim is [...] to acknowledge and take responsibility for one's expertise, to share it with others and work for the improvement of our relationships with technology, together." (Callen & Duque, 2023:110). At events, volunteer organizers welcome participants, triage devices, and match them with repair volunteers. Repairs are conducted collaboratively, with attendees guided through each step to encourage self-repair, mutual aid, and knowledge sharing.

Libraries of Things/Tools

Libraries of Things/Tools (LoTs) provide a community lending model that promotes reuse and avoids purchases. Members borrow items from a maintained catalogue, advancing public, community-based, non-commercial use and waste prevention through reuse. With the first one opened in 2020, most of Barcelona’s LoTs have received support in their early stages from local administrations.

Figure 1. Map of repair/reuse initiatives in Barcelona. Data compiled from the Barcelona City Council Open Data Portal and Idescat

4. Methods and data analysis

As noted by Purvis et al. (2025), qualitative studies in the field of grassroots collectives remain limited. To address this gap and to capture the complexity of bottom-up practices, as well as the dynamics of exclusion and inclusion within them, we adopted a qualitative research methodology. Between April 2024 and June 2025, we conducted participant observation in seven Restart Parties (RPs) and we visited ten times the five different Libraries of Things (LoTs) across Barcelona. This was complemented by 33 semi-structured interviews: 7 with RP organizers and repairers, 10 with RP participants, 4 with LoT users, 6 with LoT volunteers/employees, and 8 with other stakeholders related to circularity and repair, social economy and citizens’ participation (NGO representatives, municipal officers, local managers, and administrative employees). In addition, we organized 4 focus groups with organizers, volunteers, and users from both initiatives to facilitate collective reflection and to compare perspectives across roles. The results of these focus groups were presented in a collective feedback session with 7 attendees who had previously participated. All participants were provided with an information sheet and signed informed

consent prior to participation. Interviews lasted 20–150 minutes, were audio-recorded with permission, and transcribed verbatim. All quotes have been translated from Catalan/Spanish to English by the first author.

METHOD	ROLE	Num. of people / observations	CODES OF EXAMPLE
Semi-structured Interview	RP: Participants	10	I/RP-p1, I/RP-p2...
	RP: Volunteers	7	I/RP-v1, I/RP-v2...
	LoT: Participants	4	I/LoT-p1, I/LoT-p2...
	LoT: Volunteers / Employees	6	I/LoT-e1, I/LoT-v1,...
	Stake-holders	8	I/S1, I/S2...
Focus-Groups	RP: Participants	5	F/RP-p1, F/RP-p2...
	RP: Volunteers	5	F/RP-v1, F/RP-v2...
	LoT: Participants	7	F/LoT-p1, F/LoT-p2...,
	LoT: Volunteers / Employees	8	F/LoT-e1, F/LoT-v1...
Feed-back session Focus-Group	RP + LoT: all kind of roles	7	S/RPp1, S/RPv1, S/LoT-p1, S/LoT-v1, S/LoT-e1...
Participant Observation	Restart Parties	7	O/RP-p1, O/RP-v1...
	LoT	10	O/LoT-p1, O/LoT-v1, O/LoT-e1...

Table 1: Participants

The two initiatives were framed within the broader research project examining object circularity and grassroots circular infrastructures in Barcelona. Our fieldwork sought to cover the main active and accessible community formats of repair and reuse operating during the study period in the city of Barcelona. We focused on Restart Parties and Libraries of Things/Tools together because they constitute two consolidated and publicly visible grassroots infrastructures for circularity in Barcelona, and because they are empirically intertwined: in some neighbourhoods they share spaces, participants and resources, and function as mutually reinforcing initiatives.

The first analytic stage involved familiarization with the data corpus through repeated readings of transcripts and observational notes. Data were coded and managed using Atlas.ti software, guided by the previously mentioned research questions. Coding followed an inductive–deductive strategy (Braun & Clarke, 2006), informed both by our research questions and theoretical background (sustainability, justice and ecology, intersectionality,

inclusion/exclusion mechanisms), and by emergent patterns within the empirical material. Codes were applied to meaning units (coded excerpts) across interviews, focus groups, and fieldnotes, and were iteratively refined through constant comparison across sites and roles. In a second step, conceptually related codes were grouped into five themes that structure the analysis: (1) ageism and generational gaps; (2) ethnocentrism and institutionalized racism; (3) patriarchy and gendered divisions; (4) temporal dispossession and neoliberal productive regimes; and (5) economic and cultural powers in urban spaces (Table 2). Extracts presented in the analysis section were selected for their clarity, and explanatory value.

We ceased data collection and thematic consolidation when additional interviews/observations no longer generated substantively new codes or mechanisms relevant to our research questions, and when the five aggregate themes were sufficiently elaborated to account for the full range of inclusion/exclusion dynamics across roles and sites (theoretical saturation). Additionally, the number of interviews was connected with the limit of heterogeneity of stakeholders reached. The decision to retain five themes is related to the fact that these dimensions offered the most integrative structure for organizing intersecting mechanisms observed in the dataset, while acknowledging that boundaries between themes remain porous and relational.

Theme	Coded concepts included under the theme (examples)	coded excerpts (n)	Evidence base: sources containing ≥1 excerpt
1. Ageism and generational gaps	Adultist framings of youth; “life-stage” explanations; housing dependence & access/household mediation; scheduling and routines by age; object repertoires and youth relevance; intimidating performances of expertise connected to age	150	Interviews: 25/33 Focus groups: 3/4 Observations/fieldnotes: 9/17
2. Ethnocentrism and institutionalized racism	Catalan/Spanish dominance; outreach limits and literacy assumptions; informal solidarity among migrant networks; racialized neighbourhood climates; differentiated migrant inclusion	72	Interviews: 14/33 Focus groups: 2/4 Observations/fieldnotes: 6/17
3. Patriarchy and gendered divisions	Gender traditional roles (women as users/care managers; men as repairers/experts); gendered task sorting in organising; masculinity/pride and non-help-seeking; mansplaining/paternalism; non-mixed workshops	176	Interviews: 27/33 Focus groups: 4/4 Observations/fieldnotes: 11/17
4. Temporal dispossession and neoliberal productive regimes	Uneven distribution of free time; volunteer scarcity and organisational fragility; limited opening hours as a participation filter; scheduling as exclusionary infrastructure; “moral effort” and selective participation among politicised publics	88	Interviews: 26/33 Focus groups: 4/4 Observations/fieldnotes: 9/17

5.Economic powers and cultural normativities	Barriers linked to fees; discretionary flexibility; repair as lifestyle choice requiring cultural capital; gentrification/touristification undermining rootedness and community ties; neighbourhood character shaping participation and continuity	96	Interviews: 25/33 Focus groups: 4/4 Observations/fieldnotes: 12/17
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Table 2. Thematic Map

5. Analysis

Barcelona’s grassroots circular initiatives reveal how systems of oppression operate simultaneously to generate both exclusion and selective inclusion, shaping who participates, who is visible, and whose knowledge counts. Below we tried to systematize those dynamics, recognizing intertwined connections and overlaps between them.

5.1. Ageism and generational gaps

Repair/reuse initiatives in Barcelona are largely organized by people in midlife or older, reproducing an adult-centred orientation that sidelines adolescents and young adults (Wall, 2025). When asked about youth’s absence, participants reflected that, nowadays, adolescence is marked by an identity rooted in consumption, with few incentives to engage in community initiatives, as a kind of common and wider societal trend. As one LoT employee explained: *“In regular libraries we don’t see young people either... I think they’re in their own stage and they don’t come.”* (F/LoT-e1). Young people are depicted as being in a liminal -“their own”- phase, disconnected from the adult world. Adolescence itself was also framed as a life stage “against” adulthood, in which teenagers resist integration into adult responsibilities and instead prioritize friendships, leisure, and autonomous spaces. These opinions also echo adultist postures (Marke, 2024) and reveal how youth are socially positioned as “outside” civic participation, reinforcing exclusion from initiatives shaped by adult norms of responsibility.

Young adults under 25 were also described as difficult to engage in both initiatives, partly because of the housing crisis in Barcelona. As one interviewee noted: *“With rents in Barcelona, moving out of your parents’ place is crazy... When you start becoming independent, you have to watch your wallet, so it makes more sense to use a project like this.”*(I/LoT-e1). Without managing their own households, many young people have little immediate need for repair/reuse infrastructures and while living with parents, their participation is often mediated by an adult “registered” user, a subtler form of ageism. So, even if these initiatives contribute to saving resources, low-income individuals and young people living with their parents do not constitute the usual profile of repair/reuse participant. Nevertheless, counter-examples suggest that youth participation is contingent on context, objects, and outreach. In Sant Martí, collaborations with secondary schools led students to create their own “mini-libraries of things” within their schools. Similarly, when adolescents encountered tangible, interest-based objects such as board games or sports equipment, their

enthusiasm rose: *“They are thrilled, they come in, and it’s like: ‘Do you have board games? Do you have skates?’”* (I/S1). These examples show that youth engagement increases when initiatives resonate with their interests and socio-material worlds. Still, continuity is rare: despite initial enthusiasm, adolescents generally did not inscribe themselves as regular users of the LoT.

Organizers also reflected on their own role. Several acknowledged that current communication strategies fail to engage youth, pointing to a problematic societal generational gap: *“those of us running this are boomers and we don’t manage to engage them communication-wise”* (I/LoT-e2). They also noted practical barriers (e.g., Saturday-morning events often conflict with young people’s routines). In other words, age is not operating alone: Youth marginalisation is amplified through classed housing constraints and adult-centred institutional scripts (registration, schedules, communication channels), illustrating how adultism is produced through the intersection of life-stage, material infrastructure, and urban political economy (Marke, 2024).

Local demography plays an important role as well. Clot LoT’s family/leisure inventory and civic-centre location draw children and families, producing a more intergenerational flow, whereas Restart Parties’ electronics focus makes participation more tied to “household device ownership” and comfort with technical settings. By contrast, neighbourhoods with older populations (e.g., around the Sant Martí senior citizens’ centre) push attendance towards older age groups. As one repairer observed: *“If you look at the population data, near the community centre, where the Restart party I attend is held, it’s quite an aged population”* (I/RP-v4).

Participants pointed to generational barriers in technological authority when it comes to repair activities. Repairers, often older men, perform expertise through specialized tools and practices that may intimidate younger participants. Unlike LoTs, this technical gap is obvious in Restarters collective. One woman repairer reflected on how the presence of highly skilled, older repairers can create a barrier for less experienced youth, or even for herself, as a woman repairer, revealing how devalued identities of elderly people can gain visibility and status in particular circumstances: *“because there’s this man who puts on his magnifying glasses...and unfolds his little case that goes click, click, click, you know? He’s got all the keys, all the bits and bobs, he knows how to use all his gadgets. There’s a profile of young person who’s not going to go near him.”* (I/RP-v1). This embodied performance of expertise was described by her as *“the ‘grandpa style’: a style of authority that put me off approaching or trying to learn”* (I/RP-v1). Such a scene shows how material practices and embodied gestures can widen a generational gap within neoliberal productive societies where youth are usually cast as irresponsible and not-yet adults, while elder people might be seen as “wise people” but -as literature has highlighted- they are often marginalized after retirement due to productivist norms and demands by capitalist societies (Calasanti & King, 2015). This connects with a sort of ambivalence of repair spaces; people valorize the technical knowledge of repairers, providing social recognition and belonging, yet most of those who receive such recognition are retired older men, reinforcing ageism in knowledge. In this way, these settings simultaneously challenge productivist norms while reproducing aged and gendered hierarchies in knowledge production: older men’s retirement-status is reconfigured as a resource for authority and belonging, while simultaneously intensifying gendered and

generational hierarchies of credibility that can marginalise younger people and women/gender minorities. This illustrates how privilege and disadvantage are field-dependent and co-constituted, rather than stable attributes of identity categories (McCall, 2005; Cho et al., 2013; Hutchinson, 2000).

The “grandpa style” illustrates an intersectional dynamic in which age, gender, and technical expertise are mutually reinforcing. In these settings, repair authority is often embodied as an older, masculine performance of competence (specialised tools, magnifying glasses, calibrated gestures), which can render younger participants and women/gender minorities as peripheral learners rather than legitimate co-repairers. This is not simply a matter of “confidence” or “interest”, but a situated ordering of credibility that allocates epistemic legitimacy unevenly. At the same time, these initiatives can partially invert productivist age hierarchies by offering retired men recognition and social belonging through their technical competence. The result is an ambivalent configuration in which repair spaces contest age exclusion under neoliberal productivity norms while simultaneously reproducing age- and gendered hierarchies of expertise, consistent with intersectionality’s attention to contextually produced, co-constitutive axes of power (Cho et al., 2013)

Despite these exclusions, interviewees of repair initiatives also describe reasons for inclusion that differ by age. Older participants often draw on a past culture of repair rooted in necessity and frugality, while younger participants tend to be motivated by ecological and political concerns: “*They’ve been repairing all their live...it’s not that they’re doing anything new, they’re finding ways to keep doing what they’ve always done. And among younger people...they’re already sensitized by the current ecological situation*” (IRP-v5). In both initiatives, according to participants’ accounts, two cultural logics are deployed that could be seen as complementary to bridge and strengthen intergenerational participation by recognizing how necessity, thrift, ecological awareness, and activism intersect differently across life stages.

Participants of both initiatives constructed separately generational identities through discourses of (ir)responsibility, practical arrangements, and embodied practices of epistemic authority. Yet youth participation, while limited, shows potential when initiatives adapt their object repertoires or communication strategies. Attending these dynamics highlights the need for intergenerational approaches that resist adultism and recognize young people as full subjects of sustainability and collective life.

5.2. Ethnocentrism and institutionalized racism

Migrant residents are rendered as less visible through repair and reuse initiatives. Their absence is shaped by an ethnocentric combination of language hierarchies, class inequalities, racialized geographies and institutional practices that reflect structural barriers to access and belonging.

Local cultural codes and the predominance of Catalan and Spanish as working languages hinder the participation of neighbours with migrant backgrounds as volunteers, users, or organizers in both initiatives. A communication campaign of LoT -*Millor que meu, nostre* [‘Better than mine, ours’]- initially designed to reach migrants and youth illustrates this dilemma. As one employee explained about a particular group in her neighbourhood:

“With migrants it’s often a language issue or...embarrassment and so on, but mostly language. Some hardly speak Spanish, and some also can’t read. So we started a campaign in their languages, Urdu, Arabic, for example, but we’ve seen many of those people can’t read either. We ended up limiting the campaign to Spanish and Catalan.” (I/LoT-e3). Despite the initial efforts, this episode demonstrates how “inclusion” can become a performance but not performative and thus not effective (Ahmed, 2006), reinforcing migrants’ sense of exclusion from initiatives perceived as primarily spaces for locally rooted educated residents.

What the LoT’s employee interpreted as “embarrassment” might be connected with a real perception of exclusion, as derived from widespread and historical rights deprivations and social marginalization by which migrant people may end up internalizing the idea that services “for everyone” are not actually meant for them. As a LoT employee noted: *“They come in for the play area and they come with the kids, they pick something up, but it’s hard for them to go further. I mean, it’s hard to get migrant people to actually use the community centre...I don’t know if they see themselves here, if they say this is a space for me, too” (I/LoT-e1).* This creates a paradox: initiatives potentially most beneficial to socio-economic vulnerable groups end up being accessed mainly by those who are not primarily in need. This is not accidental but the result of a “racialised belonging” where civic spaces, as part of the infrastructural dynamics of institutionalised and invisible racism, may be implicitly coding who the “appropriate” participants are (see, MacGregor et al., 2024).

Temporal and material conditions also operate on accessibility for repair/reuse initiatives: According to a RP participant who works also as a social worker, recently arrived migrants often have fewer belongings so they don’t face the need of repair (although they might be interested in LoT), while other newcomers may not yet reached these initiatives’ communication channels (e.g. Telegram groups, Facebook pages). A LoT’s employee also reflected on how economic precarity compounds these barriers, affecting locals too: *“I don’t know if it’s a question of available time, that precarity makes you more vulnerable... Vulnerability feeds vulnerability.” (I/LoT-e1).* Lack of time, unstable work schedules, and insecurity reduce the possibility of any sustained involvement, making time constraints intersect with class.

Beyond formal participation, many migrant neighbours often rely on informal networks of solidarity and mutual support among acquaintances, rather than institutionalized or initially unknown forms of “civil society.” This reflects experiences of institutional racism connected to citizenship recognition but also collective agency and, in some cases, the persistence of cultural practices, such as everyday and informal autonomous forms of repair. In addition, the racialized urban geographies further shape participation. According to a repairer (I/RP-v4), in some neighbourhoods, strong anti-migrant and xenophobic sentiments may discourage participation, pushing migrants to *“stick within their own communities”*, while European migrants or those from wealthier Latin American countries are more present. This reflects how migration background intersects with class and racialization to produce differentiated access to community initiatives.

The absence of migrants in repair and reuse initiatives can then be materialised via intersecting structures of exclusion and resisting agency: linguistic dominance, socio-economic precarity, racialized belonging, neighbourhood-level hostility, but also informal support networks and the continuity of repair cultures within some households.

5.3. Patriarchy and gendered divisions

Gender dynamics shape who repairs, organizes, and participates. As studies showed (e.g., van der Velden, 2021; Schäggen et al., 2022) and our ethnographic work demonstrated, repair spaces often reproduce patriarchal labour divides so inclusion efforts can inadvertently reinforce assumptions of women's limited expertise and men's self-sufficient masculinities.

Although two LoTs reported the majority of their users in the 26-45 range while Restart Parties were often described as attracting "*the typical old woman*" (F/RP-v5), both initiatives show a clear majority of female users. This pattern likely reflects normative and enduring gender norms that associate women to household management, domestic economy, and care responsibilities, and frame them more often as "receivers" of technical knowledge rather than bearers of expertise. As one elder female participant explained, in the past it was her husband who fixed appliances for her; now, widowed, she must rely on repair initiatives or external help.

Another participant mentioned that the connection of care as a response to necessity and life's precariousness could explain the women's major representation of users across various circular grassroots initiatives. Similarly, a LoT's employee even talked about historical dynamics of necessity that have placed women and gender dissidents as more precarious, pushing them to create and resort to networks of collective support. Also connected to patriarchy but producing the opposite effect, some organizers of both initiatives explained men's lower presence as users by patriarchal pride: the assumption that men "should know" how to fix things discourages them from seeking help (see, Mellström, 2004), "*which isn't something usually attributed to women*" (F/RP-v4). This points to how gender norms regulate not only women's exclusion from expertise attribution but also men's exclusion from vulnerability's recognition, care, and possible collective learning.

Nevertheless, as a female repairer (I/RP-v1) noted, many women users do engage actively before seeking external help, cleaning, resetting, or even buying spare parts, but often stop short of the technical repair itself. This reflects technical interest and caring practices for household devices despite the imposed gendered limits and roles division. Volunteers also interpret women users' predominance as linked to historical cultural expectations around house care and maintenance but discouraged from developing technical competence (Pansera et al., 2024). Nonetheless, several participants point to a still incipient but progressive generational shift: "*Because some of the girls who've come by with a gadget turned out to be especially well suited to repair, people who jump in and say, 'No, let's do it this way.' But that doesn't mean they come back [as volunteers]*" (I/RP-v2). Gender divisions also affect organizers and volunteers, where women often take on administrative and facilitative roles, while men more frequently assume the position of technical repairers. When these roles are reversed, for example, with a male organiser or a female repairer, these cases are considered exceptional and celebrated, revealing how deeply rooted traditional gender roles are, but also how aware these initiatives are of them and their own limitations.

Despite this, mansplaining patterns (see also, Schäggen et al., 2022), paternalism, and infantilization are still frequently reported by female repairers. To face it, some women repairers adopt implicit strategies such as subtly taking control of a repair to demonstrate

expertise in front of male colleagues: “*So I try not to get stuck on, ‘Ugh, what an unpleasant comment he made to me’*” (I/RP-v5). Others opt for open confrontation, voicing discomfort and rendering the power dynamics visible when male colleagues seize appliances, undermine their competence, or impose unsolicited “tutorships”: “*I brought it up during the group debrief: that this guy took three appliances right out of my hands*” (I/RP-v1). These moments reveal how authority is entangled with gender roles, knowledge-power systems and age hierarchies, positioning older male repairers themselves as “experts” (Schägg et al., 2022) who teach or supervise, even sometimes against women’s wishes. These dynamics create epistemic injustice (Fricker, 2007) by reinforcing unequal knowledge positions, as women’s expertise is doubted or devalued and their tasks are often framed as “simple” or unimportant (Wajcman, 2011). Notably, these intersectional dynamics take distinct forms across the two cases: the more technical repair setting of Restart Parties tends to concentrate visible “expert” authority in repair roles, whereas Libraries of Things more often channel women and gender minorities into organisational and care-oriented labour, producing different, but connected, gendered pathways of participation and recognition.

But despite these barriers, many women users also described empowerment through collective repair/reuse practices. With initial support, they take on repairs themselves, gaining confidence and autonomy along trajectories of “trial and error” that enable them to do “new” tasks, from polishing furniture to repairing bicycles or household appliances. As a LoT’s user explained, “*I lose that feeling of ‘I don’t dare’; I do dare...I also dare to do things I didn’t do before because some man at home used to do them. Now I do it myself*” (I/LoT-p1). Hence, although gender-divided roles continue to exist, some women manage to transform the situation into technical empowerment, highlighting how repair can become a feminist practice to reclaim women’s technical agency, their autonomy and acquisition of knowledge (Faulkner, 2001), and thus undermine gender role divisions. “*All this makes us a bit more self-sufficient, so we don’t always depend on others to solve our little problems*”, said a RP’s participant (I/RP-p1). As she stated, this is not only for “gadget freaks” but for people who want to perform concrete repairs of their everyday objects.

In this sense, a RP’s participant described the event as “*the space of sharing with someone who knows more than you and gives that to you for free*” (F/RP-p1). An important effect of this is that many participants (mainly women) lose their fear of opening their electric appliances, connecting directly with Restarters’ motto: “*We don’t only repair our devices, but our relationship with them*”. As a repairer expressed, “*When someone says, ‘No, I’m going to open the TV,’ they might get scared, but if they open it and locate a component that’s failing, they get encouraged to try other things.*” (I/RP-v2). Many participants report how opening a device with guidance is illuminating: “*otherwise you open it and you see plastics and things you don’t understand. [...] That lets you, at some point, be able to open it yourself and say, ‘Ah, okay, this is this,’ and recognize parts*” (I/RP-p6).

Some initiatives adopt explicitly gender-transformative strategies by organizing non-mixed training workshops in bicycle mechanics for women, non-binary people, and migrant youth. By temporarily removing male authority and mansplaining, these highly demanded spaces enable more freely technical learning and collective empowerment. These experiences show how, although repair and reuse communities reproduce conventional gender divisions, they also contain tools to destabilise them. When roles, pedagogy and recognition are

intentionally redesigned, access to technical knowledge is broadened and women's participation is less likely to be limited to organisational roles or those of “grateful users”. However, without these strategies, even well-intentioned community spaces risk reinforcing the very hierarchies they seek to transform.

5.4. Temporal dispossession and productive neoliberal regimes

Free time is crucial for participating in repair/reuse activities, yet it is scarce and unevenly distributed in neoliberal labour systems. Precarity, care duties, and multiple jobs limit sustained involvement, particularly for those who face dispossession through overwork, vulnerability and insecurity (e.g. precarious and working-class residents, economic migrants, people with care duties -mostly women-, etc). In this sense, both participants and organizers repeatedly highlight time scarcity as a key barrier: *“Many people have so, so much work; they put in long hours; they’re exhausted...In the end it’s a bit of a vicious circle: I’m poor because, among other things, I don’t reuse; I can’t read up, get informed, and learn about reusing because I don’t have time”* (I/RP-p5). This testimony illustrates an economic-time poverty nexus, in which lack of time both stems from and reproduces socioeconomic disadvantage: those with fewer resources cannot invest in practices that could enhance sustainability or savings, reinforcing cycles of exclusion.

Temporal dispossession (Ramsay, 2020) also affects the schedule of initiatives, which depend on the availability of volunteers. This reliance produces particular profiles of volunteers, often retired men in the case of repair, and shapes the kinds of participants who attend. Limited opening hours may discourage younger people who rely on peer groups and evening or weekend availability, as well as workers with inflexible schedules. Another participant emphasized how non-immediate access to tools disrupts their routines: *“it’s not going to stop me from doing it, [but] it’s just that it has to wait”*(I/LoT-p4). Such temporal limitations also act as a sociopolitical filter: Many attendants and volunteers are highly motivated individuals with strong ecosocial awareness and progressive political commitments, who compensate for temporal scarcity through what could be called a “moral effort”. A moralized investment that distinguishes them from broader publics who may lack both the time and predisposition to prioritize repair/reuse activities over competing obligations. This reflects how temporal dispossessions filter who can meaningfully engage, further privileging those with flexible time and motivation, while excluding those constrained by work, distances and care regimes.

Time scarcity and urgencies inherent in neoliberal productivity also affect the attitudes and behaviours of both users and volunteers, with the risk that efficiency-driven logic and market practices are transferred to grassroots initiatives. As an example, despite RP aims to democratize knowledge, many users treat them as “free services” rather than collective learning spaces (Madon, 2022) and, sometimes, repairers tend to prioritize fixing over learning and knowledge sharing: *“Device arrives, device is opened, device is repaired, device leaves.”* (I/RP-v3). The resulting tension (community of practice versus service provision) means that when pedagogy is sidelined, asymmetries are reproduced, and participants leave grateful but without the desirable learning experience. Empirically, this appears as “silent” repairs or when (mainly male) repairers default to “just doing” rather than

“explaining while doing”: “*not handing over the screwdriver is a way to avoid having to explain, to avoid the risk of interacting*” (F/RP-v4).

To counter it, some other repairers reclaim more care and pedagogy, not by just sharing technical know-how and translating complex technical language, but also by chatting and communicating with participants while cultivating critical reflection on consumerism and obsolescence: “*it’s care work: the work of explaining, of knowing...what is that device like? How did they end up buying that device? How could they buy another device that’s different or better? Who are we? Who are they? What can we do so as not to take part in that crappy system?*” (F/RP-v4). This is consistent with the desire of some participants to engage more actively: “*I thought they’d make me participate more*” (I/RP-p7). Others also highlight time constraints as a limitation to deepen on the fix, “*so it’s often hard to understand why something is done in X way*” (F/RP-p5). These suggest that some exclusions and epistemic asymmetries are also caused by organizational practices affected by socio-economic logics.

The lack or need for volunteers also creates a bottleneck for expansion, or even mere daily sustainability, leading to organizational fragility and the consequent exclusions. Institutional actors linked to municipal administration point out the limits of such voluntarism: “*How can we scale them so they’re accessible to the general population?...What we can’t do is ask people to make extra efforts to meet these needs.*” (I/S2).

Neoliberal production regimes and temporary deprivation condition participation in repair/reuse activities, excluding those who have less time but who, paradoxically, are the ones who may need and benefit the most. Hence, despite the goals of inclusion by empowering participants, temporary infrastructures (built by ‘temporary authorities and their underlying power structures’, Besedovsky et al., 2019: 580) also permeate grassroots initiatives reproducing certain productive gestures, like “service” performances, and knowledge asymmetries, deeply intersected with gender, age and economic models.

5.5.Economic powers and cultural normativities

Economic inequalities, neighbourhood dynamics, and weak community ties decisively shape who participates in repair/reuse. In LoTs, participation is often filtered through stigma: sharing or borrowing may be read as “alternative” but also as “dirty,” shameful, or a refusal to perform mainstream consumerist norms. The dominant status logic equating worth with ownership and newness devalues collective use, while repair is stereotyped as either poverty-driven or the domain of “hippies” and “freaks.” In both cases, the low cost of loan fees (in the case of LoTs) and gratuity of service (in the case of RPs) may influence these derogatory stigmas. As one organiser said: “*It used to be ‘for the poor’; now it’s for the super-poor, or the super-nerds*” (F/RP-v4). Such accounts highlight how consumer culture naturalizes appearance and newness as markers of status, rendering repair/reuse stigmatized practices. From an intersectional perspective, prejudice towards these initiatives and their potential users is not merely cultural but also cuts across social class. This is exacerbated by the gentrification of neighbourhoods, as their population is replaced by another with greater income, who perceive these initiatives as irrelevant for them.

Participants themselves flag these stereotypes, warning that LoTs risk being read as services “for those lacking resources” rather than ecological alternatives for everyone: “*The idea is sustainability, not low income. But there are still many stereotypes*” (F/Lot-p4). This mirrors wider consumption cultures in which second-hand markets, until very recently, have been targeted as practices of necessity and poverty (Gregson & Crewe, 2003). At the same time, empirical material shows that motivation to participate is not purely economic. For many, it stems from ecosocial awareness, which is tied to social class, ideology and education. Importantly, these motivations often coexisted in the same accounts, suggesting that repair/reuse participation cannot be reduced to either “economic need” or “green conviction”. LoTs appear as accessibility infrastructures that articulate practical necessities with a broader critique of consumerism: “*First there’s the practical question, the pragmatism of ‘we need this; and second, the idea that it’s more important to have common goods than each of us buying every tool we need...For me, that’s the future*” (F/LoT-p6).

This duality also appears in Restart Parties, as the main motives for repairing are, on the one hand, saving money and satisfying material needs; and on the other, eco-social commitment and the rejection of consumerism as a deliberate lifestyle choice, sometimes associated with a certain cultural capital. This reflects the dual difficulty of repair in contemporary societies: cheap products (result of production offshoring and exploitative regimes, both of human and natural resources) reduce the economic incentive to repair, while moral/eco-political incentives mainly mobilise an already politicised audience. As a result, repair/reuse initiatives risk attracting mainly middle-class, environmentally conscious participants (Rogers et al., 2021). Another structural challenge is the divide between supporting the idea of repair, as a concept, and practising it, turning symbolic support into sustained and embodied routines that actually disrupt consumption.

Underlying these dynamics are broader cultural logics and very material practices of consumer capitalism: multiple “planned obsolescence” techniques (Waldman, 1993) embed power relationships and epistemic inequalities in devices limiting the possibility of autonomous repair; but also, individualism, private property, and the social prestige of consumption erode collective sustainable or sufficiency practices. A repairer highlighted that the model of economy excludes failure and is attached to the desire of buying more and new appliances, targeting old ones as “bad”: “*When an appliance breaks, people see it as the chance to buy something new...So why would you fix something old?*” (I/RP-v3). Advertising and consumer markets reinforce this orientation, cultivating a “non-repair culture” where the easiest path -less time-consuming and culturally mainstream- is disposal and replacement: “*You’ve got the super-easy path, throw it out and buy a new one, and the tortuous, uphill path: repair*” (F/LoT-e2). In this sense, research participants are aware that these initiatives swim against the tide: “*Why aren’t Restart Parties wildly successful? Because the world goes the other way.*” (I/RP-v4). In fact, one of the main achievements of RP is to make visible the politics of design (DiSalvo, 2014), and the ways manufacturers shape consumer dependence as lay users by restricting access to knowledge to expert official repairers: “*One of the things people learn, and that surprises them most, is that devices are made not to be repaired. [...] and it reveals something about the world they live in*” (I/RP-v6).

Connected to these global capitalist dynamics, the processes of gentrification and touristification in Barcelona also exacerbate who participates. In districts with high tourist

turnover or floating population, community repair/reuse initiatives struggle to sustain participation, as there is little long-term rooting or investment in local networks. Displacement and touristification lead to commodification of the city undermining community ties and the “right to the city” (Valdivielso-Navarro, 2024). As a result, collective projects lose their social infrastructure and those depending on local trust and residents continuity, like repair/reuse initiatives, remain vulnerable to these dynamics.

Despite the popular orientation of these initiatives, some economic inequalities also emerge at the micro-level of project organization, particularly around membership fees and access to LoTs. Fees are designed to help projects’ fragile sustainability -since the fees are not sufficient to cover the minimum costs of the project-, yet they can even act as barriers for those more vulnerable and with less economic resources. Fieldwork revealed contrasting practices to overcome them: At one LoT, organisers apply an informal principle of flexibility: *“no one should go without an item they need because they don’t have money. It’s true that everything ends up going through the filter of whoever’s there -me- who tries to pay attention”* (I/LoT-e2). At another LoT, by contrast, organisers maintain stricter adherence to fee protocols but offer volunteering as an alternative, which sometimes results in deeper involvement.

Therefore, neighbourhoods’ social fabric or global capitalist economy are not merely background conditions, but they actively structure the possibilities for community grassroots. Social stigma, touristification, and financial barriers intersect to produce exclusions that highlight the paradox of grassroots sustainability projects in neoliberal cities: while they resist consumerism by democratizing technical knowledge and access to circular material cultures, they are entangled with the same socio-economic hierarchies they aim to subvert.

6. Conclusions

This article applied an intersectional framework to understand how grassroots repair and reuse initiatives in Barcelona can both contest and reproduce social hierarchies through access, inclusions and exclusions. The analysis showed that interrelated axes of oppression in both macro and micro level operate and define shaping the (im)possibilities of use, participation and involvement in these initiatives.

Repair/reuse initiatives contain specific infrastructures and scripts that privilege specific publics: retired men with time and tools as repairers; middle-class eco-conscious people (Rogers et al., 2021) and older women socialized into household care as users; adults over teens; locals and native language speakers over people with migrant trajectories. But these patterns are not inevitable. They are produced by daily and very immediate conditions -such as channel communication, schedules, roles’ distribution, pedagogical performances- layered atop more structural features, such as patriarchy and gender division, institutionalized racism, capitalist economies or consumption culture. In this way, we highlighted both micro and macro (Howard & Renfrow, 2014) dynamics of exclusion that link local micro-scenes (e.g., a screwdriver not handed over, opening hours) to macro-structures and global tendencies (e.g., planned obsolescence, touristified neighbourhoods), holding together the relational picture of power that intersectionality demands.

On the other side, repair/reuse initiatives are not static sites of either empowerment or exclusion, but contested arenas of transformation that include school-based mini-libraries of objects, women narrating tool-confidence, non-mixed mechanics trainings, fee flexibility, or organizers reframing explanation as care and political education. The analysis extends intersectional environmental justice to circular grassroots practice by specifying how multiple axes of domination become operational in situated repair/reuse settings. Rather than treating exclusion as a property of individuals (“low motivation”), we traced how adultism, gendered divisions of technical expertise, linguistic dominance, neoliberal temporalities and cultural/economic powers interact to structure visibility and belonging. This moves beyond single-axis accounts and aligns with calls to embed intersectionality within sustainability transitions and waste studies (e.g., Mikulewicz et al., 2023; Acheson et al., 2024), while also complementing feminist technoscience critiques of expertise and care (e.g., Wajcman, 2011).

While the repair and reuse movements have the potential to challenge inequality and promote inclusivity in circular material cultures, they also risk reproducing existing hierarchies if these issues are not critically addressed. That’s why the integration of feminist critiques and reflexive practices is crucial to ensuring that they do not merely replicate the gender, age, knowledge or culture divides they seek to overcome, but instead contribute to a more inclusive and equitable approach to sustainability and community relations.

Building on allied scholarship and our situated analysis, we share some practical learnings on inclusivity that highlight the importance of reflexivity (Rosner, 2014) and the careful alignment of circular grassroots initiatives with users’ routines, needs and interests: (i) expanding non-mixed (women, LGBTQI+, youth, migrant) workshops to redistribute technical knowledge (Graziano & Trogal, 2017; Schäggen et al., 2022); (ii) creating facilitated and collaborative spaces to address patronizing/exclusionary practices across gender, age, and racialization; (iii) systematically inviting women and minorities to volunteer, recognizing existing skills and giving real input (Schäggen et al., 2022).

To broaden socio-economic and age profiles -countering stereotypes about poverty, freakism or hippieism- diffusion requires navigating power and aligning niches with mainstream practices (Seyfang & Smith, 2007). Thus, apart from offering long-duration loans and fee flexibility, communication could be adapted to more diverse venues (schools, libraries, primary care centres, markets), languages and media; and partner with Social Services to reach more vulnerable residents. Specifically for youth inclusion, and based on Poble Sec and Sant Martí’s LoT experience, service-learning could be embedded with educational institutions, letting students act as peer ambassadors and co-design “mini-libraries of things” on campus. This implies that initiatives need to meet people where they are, integrating reuse/repair communities into neighbourhood civic centres and running pop-up “streetfront” sessions to make them visible and easily accessible.

Given time scarcity, initiatives could also offer flexible and diverse ways of participation, allowing long-duration loans, and strengthen pedagogy: “explain while doing”, invite hands-on tool use, and share knowledge even when items aren’t fixed.

Finally, to cope with fragile voluntarism, key actors propose public–community models that pair grassroots involvement (ensuring close territorial connection and situated knowledge) with stable institutional support. This could include dedicated budget lines, infrastructure, and integration into municipal sustainability and circular-economy strategies.

Also, documenting and disseminating eco-social impacts -access to essential goods, skills gained, avoided purchases and waste, reinforced social ties- can help to build public support and social legitimacy. These alliances and management models can stabilise and expand local circular networks, set accessible tariffs for priority groups, destigmatise reuse and repair, and shift these practices from niche experiences to recognised public services and social infrastructures for urban sustainability.

Data Availability Statement

The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

Declaration of Generative AI

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT-4o in specific parts of the manuscript to improve the readability. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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